

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF INTRAVENOUS THROMBOLYSIS IN ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background : The study seeks to quantify the impact and improve the quality of life of intravenous thrombolysis of treatment in patients with Acute ischemic stroke over a certain length of time, taking consideration of demographic information such as age, gender, comorbidities, and the main clinical conditions that are affected, such as blood pressure at the time of administration, National institutional of stroke scale score, and Modified rankin score.

Methods :

This observational study, which assessed the effect of intravenous thrombolysis in acute ischemic stroke (AIS), was conducted in a retro-prospective study on 25 patients with acute ischemic stroke who received treatment with recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (rt-PA) by Intravenous thrombolysis in a tertiary care hospital.

Results :

According to a gender-based review, we included 25 patients with a mean standard deviation gender of males and females with AIS rates of 68% and 32%, respectively. The percentage of age-based assessment was determined to be 20–30%, which is not significant, and 31–40 (8%), 41–50 (32%), 51–60 (28%), 61–70 (24%), and 71–80 (8%). Drug administration time was at <3 hours (48%) and 3-4.5 hours(52%). Blood pressure at the time of administration: systolic blood pressure is < 120 (40%) and 130–170 (60%), diastolic blood pressure is <80 (56%), and 90–100 (44%). The NIHSS score at the time of admission was <14 (48%) and 15-20 (52%). After 24 hours of follow-up, the NIHSS score is <10 (64%) and 10-15 (36%). The MRS score after 1 month of follow-up was 6 (not significant), 3-5 (68%), and 0-2 (32%).

Conclusion:

Patients dealing with sudden ischemic strokes who received intravenous thrombolysis were able to endure life without any disabilities. Intravenous thrombolysis is an essential means of therapy for enhancing post-acute ischemic stroke clinical results. Hypertension is observed as the most prevalent cause of acute ischemic stroke. Compared to patients treated within 3-4.5 hours immediately after the beginning of symptoms, those treated with IV thrombolysis within less than 3 hours have a greater probability of symptom improvement.

Keyword : AIS, IV Thrombolysis, rt-PA, impact, Early administration, Time period.

INTRODUCTION

STROKE :

A stroke is the predominant cause of persistent significant handicap and now ranks as the fifth most cause fatality in the country the United States (US), having been third just a couple of years ago. Stroke is the primary trigger of mortality and hospitalization across the world, with acute ischemic stroke constituting a huge number of scenarios⁽¹⁾. Stroke symptoms might fade after a few seconds to minutes, or they are able to endure for longer. A stroke occurs when there is a quick (within sec to min) start of focused indications or symptoms of neurological dysfunctions due to ischemia ,infarction or bleeding. These focused deficits last longer than 24 hours.⁽²⁾ However, neurological symptoms are not a reliable indicator of the existence or absence of myocardial infarction , nor does their timing suggest the source of the ischemia. This is a serious problem since finding the exact origin of the symptoms is essential to receiving proper therapy.⁽³⁾ The prognosis of stroke is influenced by a wide range of factors, such as age, the severity and cause of the stroke, the site of the infarction, co-existing condition, clinical symptoms and associated consequences. Furthermore, the results of a stroke can be significantly influenced by measures like thrombolysis, stroke unit care and rehabilitation.⁽⁴⁾

ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE :

Acute ischemic stroke, which affects about 7,00,000 individuals annually, is one of the major causes of illness and fatalities in the United states. Patients with acute ischemic stroke endure treatment according to the time since the stroke began, the degree of neurologic impairment, and the results of neuroimaging.⁽⁵⁾ The NIHSS (national institute of health stroke scale) is used to quantify the severity of neurologic deficits; scores range from 0-42, with lower numbers denoting milder deficits. If the NINDS (National institute of neurological disorders and stroke) trials protocol, no neuroimaging is required prior to intravenous thrombolysis (IVT) being administered.⁽⁶⁾ The patient's arterial pressure needs to be below 180/110 mmHg both before and while receiving the treatment, and it must remain less than 170/100 mmHg throughout the preliminary twenty-four hours after the infusion. Individuals who have undertaken IVT are allowed to an intensive care unit (ICU) or a specifically designed stroke unit for close neurological observation and, if required, blood pressure management.⁽⁷⁾

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS :

- Unexpected weakness or numbness in the arms or legs and face are typically on one side of the body.
- Sudden disorientation, struggle to speak, or struggling to comprehend speech. ● Sudden difficulty seeing in one or both eyes.
- Sudden complications dizziness, loss of balance, weakness, or lack of coordination, abrupt, intense headache without apparent cause.

Only if the stroke is identified and diagnosed 3 hours after it first appears is the most effective stroke treatment accessible. If stroke sufferers do not get to the hospital in time, they perhaps are eligible for medical care.⁽⁸⁾

BE FAST

B - Balance (difficulty maintaining balance: Abrupt loss of coordination, strength or light-headedness)

E - Eye alterations: One or both eyes may experience sudden decreases in vision.

F - Face: Sudden beginning of drooping of the face, generally on one side.

A - Arm weakness : acute numbness or paralysis, usually on one side of the body in the arm.

S - Difficulty with speech : Abrupt start of trouble comprehending or speaking.

T - Time : Time matters most when treating strokes. Call 911 if you witness anybody showing any acute stroke signs and symptoms.⁽⁹⁾

THROMBOLYSIS :

On account of individuals having an instantaneous ischemic stroke ,thrombolysis with IV tissue type plasminogen activator is the sole authorized treatment. Thrombolysis splits up blood clots and stops them from forming again by using drugs or a minimally invasive treatment.⁽¹⁰⁾ Plasminogen is an inactivator beginning to undergo cleavage of a single peptide bond to become plasmin, which causes fibrin breakdown and ultimately manifests as clot disintegration. Plasmin is a relatively non-specific protease that breaks down various proteins in plasminogen, including fibrin clots and coagulation variables.⁽¹¹⁾ Thrombolytic medications are also called plasminogen activators (or) fibrinolytic drugs. While the percentage of AIS patients treated with IV tPA has risen gradually since the drug's first approval in 1996, the treatment rate remains low, with about 3.5 % to 5.3 % of all AIS patients in the US receiving IV tPA.⁽¹²⁾ The low treatment rate can be attributed to a number of factors, including medical contraindications, inadequate clinical facilities and protocol, delays in triggering medical attention and limited therapeutic time

period.⁽¹³⁾

Extending the time period of therapy may be another avenue to increase treatment rates.⁽¹⁴⁾ In 1996, the US Food & Drug Administration(FDA) authorized IV tPA as a treatment for AIS 3hr after the symptoms emerged for the first time. But an array of research has been done to assess the effectiveness and safety of prolonging the time window past 3 hours.⁽¹⁵⁾

Thrombolytic medications:

Eminase(Anistreplase), Kinlytic™(Urokinase) and Streptase (Streptokinase)

Tissue Plasminogen Activators (tPA):

TNKase®(Tenecteplase), Activase (Alteplase), and Retavase® (Retepase) To assess stroke clinical diagnosis. Treatment administration must not take the above 4.5 hours. Only when there is not visible bleeding on the computer tomography(CT) scan is IV thrombolysis advised.⁽¹⁶⁾

ADMINISTRATION :

The Alteplase dosage is 0.9 mg (maximum 90 mg) and the maximum dosage of Tenecteplase is 25 mg. Give an IV bolus containing 10% of the complete dose, and then an IV infusion containing the remaining amount for 1-6 hours. It is advised not to take any further antithrombotic medication for 24 hours. The IV thrombolysis ought to be started 3 to 4 hours after the symptoms begin. Postponing treatment can result in serious brain damage and disrupt the patient's ability to respond effectively to impulses with their motor and sensory systems.⁽¹⁷⁾

CONTRAINDICATIONS :

The bleeding diathesis includes a recent head injury or intracerebral hemorrhage(ICH).

The sustained B.P. >185/110 mmhg despite therapy.

Major surgery 14 days earlier for any further bleeding on the stomach that happened during the previous 21 days and a recent history of myocardial infarction.⁽¹⁸⁾

Numerous investigations have demonstrated a separate correlation between the risk of Symptomatically intracerebral hemorrhage (sICH) and baseline hyperglycemia or a history of diabetes.⁽¹⁹⁾

A platelet count of fewer than 1.5 lakhs is an exclusion criterion for IV rt-PA (recombinant tissue plasminogen activator), and An elevated risk of sICH has also been connected to reduced platelet counts. The possibility of statin-associated bleeding is raised by the apparent correlation between elevated sICH rates and hyperlipidemia or the use of lipid-lowering drugs. Among the cardiac risk factors for a poor outcome and the development of sICH are atrial fibrillation (AF) and heart failure (HF).⁽²⁰⁾

METHODOLOGY :

In a tertiary care hospital, this retrospective study has been carried out into reality. September 2023 to February 2024 was the study period. The inclusion criteria included that patients who were admitted to a tertiary care hospital, had an acute ischemic stroke, and were greater than 18 were eligible, regardless of gender. We included 25 patients with acute ischemic stroke who were selected based on their receiving intravenous thrombolysis within a 4:30-hour window for case selection. Ages under 18 years, pregnancy or lactation, inadequate or missing data, and hemorrhaging patients were the exclusion criteria.

The information was documented for each patient's therapy, demographic information, and results. The severity of the stroke was categorized by the provided NIHSS score, which begins at >14. The majority of the patients' scores on the NIHSS were greater than 14. After the patient had undergone a 24-hour treatment procedure, the National Institute of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score was recorded; it was less than 10 points higher than the 10-to-14 score of recovery. The present study was permitted to begin until the institute's ethical and human rights council granted authority.

In this continuous data, the mean, standard deviation, or median were used to characterize baseline attributes; for categorical data, frequencies and percentages were used. Age, the degree of the stroke, the use of thrombolysis, and other stroke sequelae, such as comorbid diseases and social habits like cigarette and alcohol consumption, were all taken into account when adjusting the length of stay (LOS) results.

RESULTS :

1.1 GENDER BASED :

Out of the 25 patients that were chosen over the course of the study, we observed 17 male and 8 female patients pertaining to inclusion and exclusion criteria. The patients who were part of the study are outlined in the table below, along with the number of AIS patients who were male and female.

Gender	Frequency Percentage
MALE	17.68%
FEMALE	8.32%

Table 1: Gender based on Acute ischemic stroke patients

1.2 AGE : We noticed that patients between the ages of 31 and 80 who take part in these studies are more susceptible to acute ischemic stroke.

Age groups	Frequency Percentage
31 - 40	2.8%
41 - 50	8.32%
51 - 60	7.28%
61 - 70	6.24%
71 - 80	2.8%

Table 2 : Age-related exposure of people with symptoms of AIS

1.3 COMORBID AND SOCIAL HABITS :

A patient with AIS susceptible to underlying medical comorbidities such as coronary artery disease(CAD), hypertension, previous cerebrovascular accident (CVA), diabetes, hysterectomy, hypothyroidism, renal calculi, and a social lifestyle including smoking and alcohol use. Patients with already present health conditions had a greater proportion of patients who passed away from their disease than people without illnesses.

Comorbidities/Social habits	Frequency	Percentage
HYPERTENSION	12	48%
CAD	5	20%
DIABETES	10	40%
HYPOTHYROIDISM	2	8%
RENAL CALCULI	1	4%
OLD CVA	1	4%
SMOKING	4	16%

ALCOHOL	7	28%
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Table 3 : Percentage based on comorbid and social habits

1.4. TIME OF DRUG ADMINISTRATION :

Patients who have an acute ischemic stroke as their underlying medical emergency. Intravenous thrombolysis is among the most notable critical medical treatments and should be administered as soon as possible, in less than 4.5 hours. The time limit for individuals registered in this health condition has been examined here.

WINDOW PERIOD (HOURS)	FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE
< 3:00	12 48%
3:00 - 4:30	13 52 %

Table 4 : Based on the time window given to people who received treatment within the allotted period

1.5 BLOOD PRESSURE DURING THE PROCEDURE FOR THE

ADMINISTRATION OF INTRAVENOUS THROMBOLYSIS (IVT) When administering IV thrombolysis, blood pressure is a key factor. Blood pressure is higher than 180/120 mmHg is not recommended to be administered to IVT because it can result in hemorrhage. Consequently, we have examined blood pressure during IVT.

Blood Pressure(mmhg)	Frequency Percentage
Systolic B.P (Mm)	
< 120	10 40%
130 - 170	15 60%
Diastolic B.P (Hg)	
< 80	14 56%
90 - 100	11 44%

Table 5:

Percentage of patients whose blood pressure during the treatment had both systolic and diastolic.

1.6 THE NIHSS SCORE AT THE TIME OF BEING ADMITTED : Prior to starting treatment, we examined the patient's NIHSS score at the time of admission with onset of symptoms.

NIHSS SCORE	FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE
09 - 14	12 48%
15 - 20	13 52%

Table 6 : Percentage of the patient’s NIHSS score at the time of admission, onset of symptoms

1.7 NIHSS SCORE FOLLOWING A 24-HOURS ADMISSION :

In addition, we examined the NIHSS score 24 hours following the patient's admission.

NIHSS SCORE	FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE
< 10	16 64%
10 - 15	9 36%

Table 7 : Percentage of NIHSS Score after 24 hours of admission

1.8 MODIFIED RANKIN SCORE (MRS) :

To ensure patient impairment and quality of life, we have examined the modified rankin score of the patients following intravenous thrombolysis.

MRS	FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE
0 - 2	14 56%
3-5	11 44%
6	0 0

Table 8 : Percentage of modified rankin score

DISCUSSION:

Strokes are actually the second most common cause of fatality and constitute the third most common incidence of impairment globally. The intent of the current investigation is to determine whether a quality improvement programme can shorten the time it takes for intravenous thrombolysis in cases of AIS. Multiple polls indicate that the greatest age group encompasses the ages of 50 and above (62%), while the lowest age group is less than 50 and under 38%. In comparison, people with co-occurring conditions such as social habits (44%), cardiovascular diseases (20%), diabetes (40%), hypertension (48%), and other conditions (16%) are more likely to have AIS. This increases their risk of stroke and the effects it has on modifying their way of life.

CONCLUSION :

The subject of this study finds that early detection of stroke symptoms is advantageous for immediate therapy. It is advised to provide intravenous thrombolysis exclusively to patients who arrive at a medical emergency within 4.5 hours of the onset of symptoms. Patients dealing with sudden ischemic strokes who received intravenous thrombolysis were able to endure life without any disabilities. Intravenous thrombolysis is an essential means of therapy for enhancing post-acute ischemic stroke clinical results. Hypertension is observed as the most prevalent cause of acute ischemic stroke.

Compared to patients treated within 3-4.5 hours immediately after the beginning of symptoms, those treated with IV thrombolysis within less than 3 hours have a greater probability of symptom improvement.

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